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Press release

A Crowdsourced Ecosystem to fight Childhood Cancer

The consortium of **EU4CHILD** (EUropean foundations for CHILdhood Cancer Ecosystem) is pleased to announce the launch of an ambitious joint initiative selected and granted by the European Commission as a PPPA-AG (Pilot Project & Preparation Action Grant).

EU4CHILD's ultimate goal is the creation of a multi-purpose crowdsourced ecosystem for paediatric cancer care, able to support a set of top-quality, evidence-based **Artificial Intelligence (AI) services** to accelerate an early **diagnosis, prognosis** and personalised **treatment and care** of several types of paediatric cancer. We seek to connect key European stakeholders in childhood cancer care by means of eXplainable AI.

In 2020, over 15,500 children and adolescents were diagnosed with cancer in Europe and over 2,000 lost their lives to it. Paediatric cancer represents the leading cause of death from disease in children beyond the age of one: Leukaemia, accounting for 33% of all cancers, followed by brain tumours and other solid tumours like Neuroblastoma, Nephroblastoma and sarcomas are the most common types.

Most paediatric cancers are clinically and genetically different compared to adult cancers, demonstrating the need for childhood-specific genomic studies, datasets and therapeutic strategies. Early detection is key, since paediatric cancers are growing fast and may have spread to other parts of the body by the time they are diagnosed. Up to 30% of children affected by cancer suffer severe long-term consequences. So comprehensive care, treatment and follow-up are essential to help them through a good recovery and improve their quality of life.

To achieve this, EU4CHILD will improve the availability of **easy to use, eXplainable AI tools** for precise diagnosis, personalised treatment selection and outcome prediction in children with cancer, which will be particularly important in selecting patients for

personalized medicine, while also empowering patients and families and facilitating the transfer of knowledge and expertise globally.

EU4CHILD's commitment towards community building, ethical research, patient-centricity, data-driven innovation and knowledge transfer will culminate in the creation of an **interoperable and distributed EU data marketplace for action on paediatric cancer**, built around three cornerstones:

- A multi-perspective State-of-the-Art, complemented by a **multidisciplinary roadmap** collecting the challenges, needs and open issues arising from patients, health professionals, healthcare institutions, national health systems and AI specialists.
- A one-stop portal to host and curate an **EU-wide knowledge base** for childhood cancer, providing insights on the disease and liaising future opportunities for collaboration.
- An **engaged community of stakeholders** that will develop working streams with digital initiatives designed to support diverse paediatric cancer pathways.

Childhood cancers are rare diseases. The only effective way to push forward research and ensure better care for children with cancer is through active collaboration, transparent communication and a solid knowledge exchange.

During its 18-month run, **6 partners from 4 European countries** will join forces to make EU4CHILD a reality. The team includes key partners from research and the healthcare sector: combining experts in AI and paediatric oncology with impact and community building specialists.

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